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HYDROMODULUS ZONING OF IRRIVATED LAND OF SOUTH KARAKALPAKSTAN

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ANNNOTATION

Global climate change not only negatively affects the water world, but also aggravates the problem of fresh water shortage. This is the effective use of water resources in agriculture, the development and implementation of water-saving irrigation regimes and technologies.

Key words: Hydromodule, irrigation, zoning southern Karakalpakstan.

World scientists are looking for additional water resources during global climate change, with water shortages and land reclamation deterioration, conducting research into the creation of water-saving irrigation technologies and optimal irrigation regimes for cotton, and the introduction of modern digital technologies. By using geographic information technologies (GIS), the problems of the negative consequences of water shortages in the world are being solved; hydromodular zoning and the development of an optimal crop irrigation regime are promising directions.

Approved by the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan PP-6024 dated July 10, 2020, "On approval of the concept of development of the water sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020 - 2030", improvement of the water resources management system, introduction of "Smart Water" technology and similar digital technologies in keeping records of water use and water consumption, the further expansion of the use of water-saving irrigation technologies when growing crops is emphasized; based on water-saving irrigation technologies and irrigation regimes under various soil-climatic conditions, recommendations on watering rates and irrigation regimes have been developed. As a result of a radical change in the water use system, when using alternation of cotton and winter wheat, due to the continuous operation of irrigation networks throughout the year and an increase in the load on drainages due to filtration losses, increase in the area of hydromorphic soils.

The degree of knowledge of the problem. In our republic, extensive scientific research was carried out by such scientists as S.N. Ryzhov, M.N. Mednis, N.F. Bespalov, F.N. Rakhimbaev, K.M. Mirzajonov, A.E. Avliyokulov, B. S. Mambetnazarov, Sh. N. Nurmatov, M. Kh. Khamidov, Sh. Duchemin B., Cai T., Xu H., Peng D., Yin Y., Yang W., Brown M.J., W.D.Kemper, Coolidge P.S., Goldhamer D.A., Guttman Joseph, Jeffrey T. Baker, Dennis C. Gitz, Marx D., Hutter J., Mohan Reddy Junna, Stringham G.E., Walker W., Stringham J., Wallende on studying the influence of irrigation regime, methods and technologies for irrigating cotton on water-physical and agrochemical properties of soil, plant development, productivity and its quality in irrigated agriculture.

To assess the possible increase in water consumption on irrigated lands due to changing climatic conditions, in order to ensure the effective use of water resources, there is insufficient research on hydromodulation y zoning of irrigated lands and development of scientifically based

optimal irrigation regimes for each hydromodular region using modern geographic information system (GIS) technology.

The subject of the study is the hydromodular zoning of irrigated lands in the southern zone of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, an electronic map of areas and the influence of a scientifically based irrigation regime for cotton water use plans for water consumers, efficient use of water resources, for the productivity of 1 m³ of water, cotton yield.

In 2018-2020 in the southern zone of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, according to the Karakalpakstan reclamation expedition, the areas of irrigated land in hydromodular areas were determined, as well as using GIS technology when creating electronic maps in the context of ions, the results of the study and calculations are presented.

Hydrogeological and soil conditions of the research object were analyzed on the basis of 1217 groundwater monitoring wells and their passports in South Karakalpakstan, under Karakalpaks such a reclamation expedition. According to research, groundwater with a depth of more than 3 meters in the southern Republic of Karakalpakstan makes up 2.14% of the territory. Groundwater with a depth of 2-3 meters makes up 15.86% of the total area. The remaining 82.01% falls on areas of groundwater 1-2 meters deep.

Using the ArcGIS program to create electronic digital maps of soils according to their mechanical composition, to carry out geovisualization of groundwater level indicators based on the field layer and entering into this electronic This is a digital map of the results of periodically conducted field research, a hydromodule of the section of the area based on the latest reliable data from electronic maps of the area's zoning (pic. 1).

Figure 1. Electronic map of irrigated lands in the Beryniya region.

Based on this map, the southern regions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan are divided into 0.50% I, 1.36% II, 0.28% III, 4.98% IV, 9.5% V, 1.37% VI, 25.78% VII, 34.37% VIII and 21.86% belong to the IX hydromodular region. The largest 34.37% of irrigated lands in the southern regions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan are in the VIII hydromodular region (Table 1).

Table 1

Distribution of irrigated lands in the southern regions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan by hydromodular areas, %

Regions	Irrigated area,	Thousand hectares, Gidromodulny district								
		I	II	III	IV	V	VI	VII	VIII	IX
Beryniy	33,32	0,51	0,99	0,00	2,13	2,28	1,29	34,18	27,79	30,82
Tyrtkul	30,38	0,86	2,21	0,43	8,56	3,62	2,27	17,87	30,15	34,04
Amudaryo	38,43	0,39	0,94	0,60	2,76	3,59	0,00	44,26	47,46	0,00
Ellik kala	34,10	0,29	1,44	0,06	7,10	28,45	2,20	3,78	29,79	26,89
Total	136,23	0,50	1,36	0,28	4,98	9,50	1,37	25,78	34,37	21,86

Conclusions

1. In the Republic of Karakalpakstan there are 136.23 thousand. hectares of irrigated lands in the southern regions belong to one soil-climatic zone - the desert zone, within this zone there are three soil-reclamation areas, as well as according to the location of the mechanical composition of irrigated lands in the aeration layer and the location groundwater levels are divided into 9: I (0, 55%), II (1.36%), III (0.28%), IV (4.98%), V (9.5%), VI (1.37%), VII (25.78%), VIII (34.37%) and IX (21.86%) hydromodular regions.
2. According to the distribution of irrigated lands by hydromodular areas in the southern regions of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, in the main irrigated lands during the growing season at a groundwater level of 1-2 m of the total area it amounted to 25.78% VII, 34.37% VIII 21.86% hydromodular districts.
3. Creation of electronic maps in the context of regions using GIS technology of irrigated lands in the southern zone of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. These maps allow you to create plans for water use, limited water use, determine irrigation regimes for agricultural crops and soil leaching regimes, and promptly introduce them changes.

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